

The History and Evolution of the Formation of International Institutions Regulating Islamic Finance From a Legal and Organizational Perspective

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Annotation: *This article analyzes the international Islamic financial institutions, the history of their formation and development, goals and objectives, scope of activity and development trends. Also, opinions and comments about the activities of these organizations in Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, implemented and ongoing projects, methods and sources of financing are provided on the basis of the article. Proposals and recommendations are provided for the development of cooperation with large Islamic financial institutions in Uzbekistan.*

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Islamic finance is a rapidly growing sector in the global financial market, encompassing a range of financial activities that adhere to the principles of Islamic law (Shariah). Islamic financial institutions play an important role in promoting ethical and interest-free financial operations, enabling the participation of both Muslims and non-Muslims in the global economy. This article aims to explore the history, development, legal and organizational regulations of international Islamic financial institutions, highlighting their main objectives and functions.

The roots of Islamic finance trace back to the early days of Islam. The Prophet Muhammad established principles of fairness, equity, and ethical conduct in financial transactions of that time. These principles, further elaborated in the Quran and the teachings of the Prophet Muhammad, formed the foundation of Islamic finance. However, the modern Islamic finance industry began to take shape in the 20th century, primarily as a response to the need for an alternative financial system compatible with Islamic principles.

In 1963, the establishment of the first Islamic bank, the Mit-Ghamr Savings Bank in Egypt, marked the beginning of the formal operations of Islamic financial institutions. This was followed by the founding of the Dubai Islamic Bank in 1975, which set the precedent for subsequent Islamic banks around the world. The increasing demand for financial products and services that comply with Shariah led to the emergence of various international Islamic financial institutions, including Islamic banks, Takaful (Islamic insurance) companies, investment funds, and Sukuk (Islamic bonds) issuers.

What is the main purpose of establishing international Islamic financial institutions? What objectives and functions do these international organizations pursue?

Below are the primary objectives and functions of establishing Islamic financial institutions: a) **Promoting Shariah-compliant financial products:** The main objective of international Islamic financial institutions is to develop and offer a wide range of financial products and services that adhere to Shariah principles. These products include Islamic financing, investments, savings, and insurance solutions that avoid interest (Riba), excessive uncertainty (Gharar), and activities deemed unethical or unjust. b) **Contributing to economic development:** Islamic financial institutions aim to contribute to sustainable economic development by providing a fair and stable financing system. They support responsible investments and infrastructure development that align with the principles of economic justice and community welfare, as well as entrepreneurship and social welfare projects. c) **Enhancing financial inclusivity:** Islamic financial institutions strive to enhance financial inclusion by reaching out to underserved individuals and communities with ethical and accessible financial services. This extends beyond the Muslim population and encourages financial participation from people of various faiths and cultures who value ethical principles and social justice. d) **Ensuring compliance with regulatory frameworks:** International Islamic financial institutions adhere to strict regulatory and legal frameworks to ensure Shariah compliance and maintain financial stability. Regulatory bodies oversee the operations of Islamic banks, Takaful companies, and other institutions both at the national and international levels, ensuring adherence to Shariah governance, risk management, and disclosure requirements.

Several international Islamic financial institutions play a key role in achieving these objectives and functions:

Islamic Development Bank (IDB): Established in 1975, IDB is a multilateral development finance institution. Its main goal is to support the economic development and social progress of member countries and Muslim communities worldwide. IDB funds infrastructure projects, agriculture, education, health, and investments in member countries, and supports trade and investment through trade financing, venture capital funds, and risk-sharing mechanisms.

Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI): AAOIFI is a standard-setting body for the global Islamic finance industry. It develops and implements Shariah, accounting, auditing, governance, and ethical standards for Islamic financial institutions. AAOIFI plays a crucial role in enhancing transparency, consistency, and harmonization of Islamic financial practices across jurisdictions, fostering industry stability and growth.

International Islamic Financial Market (IIFM): IIFM focuses on developing standardized legal documentation, master agreements, and product templates for the Islamic finance industry. It plays a crucial role in standardizing Islamic capital market instruments such as Sukuk, Islamic derivatives, and risk management products.

Islamic Corporation for the Development of the Private Sector (ICD): Part of the IDB Group, ICD is a multilateral development finance institution aimed at promoting sustainable economic growth in member countries by financing private sector projects and providing technical assistance and advisory services. ICD supports various sectors, including infrastructure, agriculture, manufacturing, and services, to foster economic diversification and entrepreneurship.

General Council for Islamic Banks and Financial Institutions (CIBAFI): CIBAFI is an international non-profit organization representing the interests of Islamic financial institutions globally. It focuses on promoting understanding and cooperation among stakeholders, including financial institutions, regulators, and industry experts. CIBAFI undertakes research, advocacy, and capacity-building initiatives to encourage healthy growth and governance in the Islamic finance industry.

Liquidity Management Centre (LMC): LMC is an international Islamic finance institution specializing in liquidity management and offering innovative, Shariah-compliant short-term investment solutions. It provides Islamic banks and financial institutions with short-term funding tools, investment products, and custom treasury solutions, addressing liquidity management challenges and optimizing fund deployment.

Islamic Corporation for the Insurance of Investment and Export Credit (ICIEC): A key member of the IDB Group, ICIEC specializes in offering Shariah-compliant insurance and reinsurance solutions for investment and export credit risks. It supports cross-border trade and investments by covering political and commercial risks, encouraging economic growth in member countries, and bolstering international business confidence.

These institutions collectively contribute to the global development, regulation, and promotion of Islamic finance, fostering economic growth, innovation, and ethical financial practices.

They collectively aim to contribute to the expansion and sustainability of Islamic finance as an alternative financial system that adheres to Shariah principles. In several leading Muslim countries, national Islamic financial organizations operate at the level of these international Islamic financial institutions and also have a significant impact on global Islamic financial relations. For example:

Guidance Financial Group: This group is a global provider of Shariah-compliant real estate investment and financial solutions. It offers a range of services, including residential financing, commercial property financing, and fund management. Guidance Financial Group operates in the United States, the Middle East, Canada, and the United Kingdom, and is known for offering convenient and ethical financing options for real estate.

Bank Negara Malaysia (Central Bank of Malaysia): Bank Negara Malaysia plays a crucial role in regulating and developing the Islamic finance sector in Malaysia. It supports the establishment and growth of Islamic banking institutions, facilitates the issuance of Islamic bonds (Sukuk), and exercises regulatory oversight to ensure compliance with Shariah principles. The bank also conducts research and development activities to promote Islamic finance in Malaysia.

Dubai Islamic Bank (DIB): DIB is the first Islamic bank in the UAE and one of the largest Islamic banks in the world. It offers a comprehensive range of Shariah-compliant banking services, including retail, corporate, investment, and treasury products. DIB's operations encompass project financing, trade finance, wealth management, and tailored financial solutions for personal and corporate needs.

Kuwait Finance House (KFH): Headquartered in Kuwait, KFH is a leading Islamic bank offering a variety of Shariah-compliant banking and financial services, including retail and commercial banking, investment products, treasury services, and asset management. KFH has a significant presence in Kuwait and branches across the Middle East, Turkey, Malaysia, and Europe.

Al Rajhi Bank: Al Rajhi Bank is one of the largest Islamic banks and the world's largest Islamic commercial bank by assets. Based in Saudi Arabia, it offers Shariah-compliant banking products and services such as financing, deposits, trade finance, and investment banking activities. Al Rajhi Bank serves personal, business, and corporate clients both locally and internationally.

Takaful Malaysia: Takaful Malaysia is a leading Islamic insurance (Takaful) company operating in Malaysia and internationally. It provides a wide range of Shariah-compliant general and life insurance products, including auto, travel, health, and savings plans. The company follows a cooperative model where participants contribute to a fund to protect against various risks.

These are just a few examples of international Islamic financial institutions with distinct areas of focus and activities. Together, they contribute to the growth and development of the Islamic finance

industry, addressing the needs of various clients seeking ethical and Shariah-compliant financial solutions.

Cooperation with international Islamic financial institutions is also crucial for Central Asia, including Uzbekistan. Notably, several major projects in the region have been undertaken by the Islamic Development Bank (IDB) and others are planned for the future.

The Islamic Development Bank (IDB) actively participates in funding and implementing various development projects in Central Asia, including Uzbekistan. Some general examples of IDB initiatives in the region include:

Completed projects:

- **Tuyamuyun Hydroelectric Power Station:** IDB funded the construction of this hydroelectric power station in Uzbekistan to increase energy production and meet the growing demand for electricity.
- **Bukhara Solar Power Plant:** IDB supported the development of a solar power plant in the Bukhara region of Uzbekistan, aimed at promoting renewable energy sources and reducing the country's reliance on fossil fuels.
- **Rural Solid Waste Management Project:** IDB funded a project aimed at improving waste management systems in rural areas of Uzbekistan, addressing environmental issues and promoting sustainable development.

Upcoming projects:

- **Uzbekistan National Highways Improvement Project:** IDB has committed funds to improve the national highway network in Uzbekistan, focusing on enhancing transportation infrastructure and facilitating regional connectivity.
- **Water Supply and Sanitation Project:** IDB pledged support for a project aimed at improving access to clean water and sanitation facilities in several regions of Uzbekistan, promoting public health and sustainable development.
- **Agricultural Financing Project:** IDB expressed interest in allocating funds to develop the agricultural financing system in Uzbekistan to boost productivity and support rural livelihoods.

Uzbekistan joined the Islamic Development Bank in September 2003 during the annual meeting held in Ouagadougou. It also became a member of the **Islamic Corporation for the Development of the Private Sector (ICD)** in 2004. The IDB representative office in Uzbekistan began its activities in October 2006. Negotiations for membership in the **Islamic Corporation for the Insurance of Investment and Export Credit (ICIEC)** and the **International Islamic Trade Finance Corporation (ITFC)** are ongoing. The total amount of projects approved by the IDB Group for Uzbekistan has surpassed \$2 billion. Financing methods include **Istisna** (build-to-order contracts), **Murabaha** (deferred payment sales), and leasing. Notably, construction financing plays a significant role in IDB projects in Uzbekistan, encompassing improvements in agricultural infrastructure and the construction and renovation of educational institutions.

The ICD's financing primarily focuses on Murabaha agreements, with more than \$200 million allocated to date. Despite Uzbekistan being the last CIS country to join the IDB and ICD, it ranks first in terms of portfolio volume in the region. In March 2018, a framework agreement worth \$100 million was signed between the Government of Uzbekistan and the ITFC to finance trade operations. This enabled the ITFC to finance trade projects before Uzbekistan's official membership and so far, ITFC has provided Murabaha financing lines to Asia Alliance Bank, Trustbank, and Kapitalbank.

Ongoing negotiations for membership in ITFC and ICIEC are expected to be concluded by the first half of 2019. Currently, ICIEC has several planned projects for Uzbek companies.

In conclusion, there are many planned projects and ongoing discussions related to collaboration with Islamic financial institutions, indicating the need to continue developing a range of legal and organizational mechanisms.

Firstly, strengthening the regulatory framework is a top priority. Developing and enhancing the legal framework for Islamic finance in Uzbekistan is crucial. This may involve establishing specific rules and guidelines that ensure compliance of Islamic financial products and services with the country's legal and regulatory framework. By providing a clear and comprehensive regulatory environment, Uzbekistan can facilitate the entry of major Islamic financial institutions and foster partnerships.

Secondly, promoting investments and fostering collaboration: Uzbekistan can offer incentives and opportunities for major Islamic financial institutions to invest in the country. This could be achieved through tax incentives, access to special investment zones, or measures that ensure business ease. Such incentives could encourage Islamic financial institutions to explore investment opportunities across various sectors of the Uzbek economy, leading to productive collaborations and mutually beneficial agreements.

Thirdly, promoting awareness and capacity building: Raising awareness about Islamic finance among government officials, entrepreneurs, and the general public in Uzbekistan is a key starting point. This could be accomplished by organizing conferences, seminars, and workshops on Islamic finance, inviting experts from major Islamic financial institutions to share their knowledge and experiences. Additionally, training courses and certification programs in Islamic finance could be offered to professionals in relevant fields. By building a knowledgeable workforce, Uzbekistan can create an enabling environment for partnerships with major Islamic financial institutions and effectively leverage Islamic financial tools for its economic development.

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